

The Effect of the Application of Graphic Design and Social Media Marketing On Increasing Brand Loyalty

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Jennifer Angela Pangestu**

Post Graduate Student: Department of Management, faculty of Economic and Business, Universitas Tanjungpura.

Corresponding Author's E-mail: jenniferangela@student.untan.ac.id

Lecturers

⁽²⁾**Helma Malini**-Lecturer, Department of Management, faculty of Economic and Business, Universitas Tanjungpura. ⁽³⁾**Nur Afifah** -Lecturer, Department of Management, faculty of Economic and Business, Universitas Tanjungpura. ⁽⁴⁾**Hasanudin**-Lecturer, Department of Management, faculty of Economic and Business, Universitas Tanjungpura. ⁽⁵⁾**Dody Pratama Marumpe**-Lecturer, Department of Management, faculty of Economic and Business, Universitas Tanjungpura.

Abstract:

In this era, integrated social media has become one of the most popular marketing strategies companies use. The developments of technology create new mechanisms and communication tools in the modern marketing world, where it is easier for companies to reach and communicate with actual and potential consumers. This study aimed to explore the impact of social media marketing (SMM) activities, brand image, and graphic design in building KFC consumers' loyalty in Indonesia.

The primary source of data collection was obtained from 250 KFC respondents in Indonesia who were chosen using a purposive sampling technique, while the analysis technique used was SEM AMOS 26. The main findings in this study indicated that effective use of social media marketing in the presence of graphic design would increase brand image and consumer loyalty. The relationship between brand image and brand loyalty was also very effective. The resulting output also demonstrated that brand image acted as an arbitrage between social media marketing and graphic design for brand loyalty.

Keywords: brand image; brand loyalty; graphic design; KFC ;social media marketing

1. Introduction

Social media significantly influences how people live and how companies do their business. The conventional ways of interacting between customers and brands have been intensively reversed thanks to the empowerment of consumers by social media. Therefore, the methods of consulting each other between the two parties have also changed dramatically (Christodoulides & Jevons, 2011; Christodoulides, 2009). Traditionally, brand managers will be the ones who form ideas and convey messages through available channels to achieve business goals of attracting customers, which will result in higher sales volumes and better benefits (Patino et al., 2012). However, nowadays, social media platforms shift the scalability of influence to the other side of this relationship and how consumers decide to choose, share, and value information (Smithee, 2011). Marketing channels have virtually accessed 2.77 billion internet users worldwide through newly defined methods (Ebrahim, 2020).

Media such as Instagram has managed to have 500 million daily users, while Twitter with around 166 million daily users worldwide in the first quarter of 2021. However, the most used social media platform is Facebook, which has more than 2.85 billion active users (Tankovska, 2021). Statistically and specifically, from 100% of the generational population, U.S. millennials are the most users of social media, namely 90.4%, followed by Generation X (77.5%) and Baby Boomers (48.2%) (Lipsman, 2019). The figures also reveal the strategies brands use to target their customers, and up to 73% of marketers believe social media marketing is "somewhat effective" or "very effective" for their business (Buffer, 2019). In general, many brands run and grow through their social media channels by communicating, sharing, and engaging with their customers, hoping they can create brand awareness, leading to sales growth. Similarly, as shown in a recent study, 93% of social media users prefer to engage with companies via these virtual platforms as they are more cost-effective and can reach more customers when compared to other traditional channels, such as radio, newspapers, or magazines. (Amersdorffer et al., 2012) .

Digital marketing has a vast scope. When people mention digital marketing, they talk about I.T., social media, trends, business, advertising, and the internet community. This advancement of technology is a concrete manifestation of a phenomenon where consumer behavior has now experienced a shift. Consumers want to get their needs and wants more practically and quickly. It is like an epidemic and is a new trend in today's modern society. A graphic design strategy is essential for a business to build its image and remain visually consistent throughout marketing efforts. Using the Art of graphic design will help enhance a company's brand identity and brand recognition. The graphic design optimizes your marketing efforts across all channels and is key to building a professional brand. Consistent marketing collateral allows your brand to be easily recognized and lets your customers and clients quickly become familiar with what your company has to offer. The comfort that clients and customers get through consistent marketing will eventually lead to credibility. Your brand must have a strong visual foundation to communicate its trust in its offerings and expertise. It allows customers to engage with your business more frequently, which in turn leads to stronger customer relationship management (CRM).

Advertising is expected to stimulate consumers to consume highly and cultivate extravagance. Advertisements that promote products from KFC with a persuasive communication approach have visuals that contain meaning. Visuals used as a language of communication can attract large audiences. Thus, communication connects visuals or images at the level of billboards, banners, posters, and the like as the nonverbal communication language. It can be said to be the language of visual communication. However, what visuals can display persuasive communication like in KFC advertisements. The communication behind this visual language makes researchers interested in researching KFC advertisements because it is to provide understanding to the community.

2. Literature review

Social Media Marketing refers to online applications, platforms, and media that facilitate interaction, collaboration, and content sharing (Richter, Koch 2007). Social media Marketing can also be defined as activities, practices, and behavior among communities of people who gather online to share information, knowledge, and opinions using conversational media (Safko, Brake 2009). Social Media Marketing is one of the tools widely used in communication marketing, generating brand-related consequences, including brand awareness and customer engagement (Bento et al., 2018).

Social Media Marketing is one of the most common and effective marketing communications disseminated on social media platforms (Straker et al., 2015a, 2015b). Social Media Marketing contains promotional information posted on social media or shared to build brand image and generate sales (Okazaki and Taylor, 2013). It is because Social Media Marketing requires unique content that combines a strong persuasive appeal and positive implications on Brand Image and action-stimulating appeals that directly influence consumer intentions and behavior toward a brand (Hilman et al., 2017). With the recent dominance of social media as a marketing platform, it has become an essential vehicle for promotional information, otherwise known as selling social media promotional content (Okazaki and Taylor, 2013; Ahmed and Zahid, 2014; Kim and Ko, 2012).

Graphic Design is defined as communicating ideas through images and/or text. In other words, graphic design is about effective visual communication (Graver & Jura, 2012). Examples of graphic design in libraries include bookmarks, pamphlets, posters, brochures, Web pages, logos, and banners. The graphic design process refers to the process by which a designer conceptualizes, creates, approves, and finally delivers the design. Meanwhile, best practice refers to practices that have proven to be effective in terms of design.

The design logo is used to add customer value. The logo emphasizes the outward appearance and makes people interested. Good design can contribute to product usability as well as appearance. Attractiveness is used to influence consumers' feelings towards products or services, especially by displaying advertising messages that can persuade and retain consumers' memories of the products offered. The attractiveness of advertising can increase the success of delivering messages to targets (Leelayudthyothin, 2022).

Social Media Marketing has become a center for promoting goods and services that enable marketers to communicate with customers actively. Also, it has shifted the previous one-way communication channel to

a two-way one, allowing more customer engagement and creating a sense of equality between consumers and their brands (Evans, 2011). Moreover, social media-based communications provide consumers with relevant information and reduce their search efforts (Merisavo and Raulas, 2004; Laroche et al., 2013). Based on the different emerging definitions for social media marketing (SMM), SMM can be generalized into several points. Firstly, SMM takes advantage of social media platforms and uses them as a marketing tool to create two-way communication between marketers and customers by providing valuable offers to gain higher brands/products or service attention and encourage consumer participation. Secondly, Social Media Marketing enables interaction, content sharing, and information diffusion (Chang, Yu, & Lu, 2015). Third, Social Media Marketing facilitates user responses to brands ranging from beliefs or perceptions (Chi, 2011; Dwivedi et al., 2015), satisfaction (Sano, 2014), or behavioral responses such as product reviews, purchase intentions, and loyalty (Kim & Ko, 2012, 2010).

Social media marketing is considered an effective tool for developing relationships with customers (Choi, Fowler, Goh, & Yuan, 2016). In addition, this interaction will build trust and eliminate the uncertainty that might prevent customers from being loyal to a brand (Khadim et al., 2018). Companies utilize social media platforms to communicate, interact, engage with consumers, and provide value and experience. Consumer perceptions through marketing activities carried out by companies in an online context can increase consumer confidence. The positive effects of social media marketing activities have been proven empirically (for example, Ismail, 2017). Marketing through social media can stimulate consumer loyalty to a brand (Ebrahim, 2020).

Brand loyalty is defined as a process of responding to customer behavior and psychological reactions, which means that brand loyalty is positively related to one's behavior and attitudes (Jacoby and Kyner, 1973). However, in fact, (Tepeci, 1999) states, "a person's behavior (such as repeat purchases) is influenced psychologically." As brand loyalists, consumers usually buy the same products and services. For fast food restaurants, consumers consciously go to the same restaurant.

Graphic design is a visual representation of a brand that can provide functional benefits for a company. Attractive designs can help customers identify and choose brands easily. Attractive and innovative web designs can become the basis for marketers to provide detailed information to fulfill potential purchase intentions among online buyers (Din et al., 2016). Design with good aesthetics in an advertisement can attract customers and build emotional relationships to increase customer loyalty to a brand (Atak, 2021).

Brand Image is a mental image or perception of a brand, branded product, or service and includes the symbolic meaning that consumers associate with the specific product or service attributes (Dobni & Zinkhan, 1990; Padgett & Allen, 1997). Brand image has a positive effect on brand loyalty because people are loyal to brands whose image is already in their minds. Fatma et al. (2015), having good recognition and a positive image in customers' minds will help consumer loyalty. If awareness of the brand increases, so will brand trust, increasing the purchase purpose. Therefore, buyers of a product can make rules of decisions to buy well-known and established brand products. Arman (2020) shows that there is a positive relationship between brand image and brand loyalty.

3. Theoretical basis

In previous research, Godey et al. (2016) have discovered that social media marketing does not have an adequate role in increasing perceptions of brand image and brand loyalty among consumers. However, according to Ebrahim's (2019) research, social media marketing has a vital role in increasing consumers' perception of brand image and brand loyalty. Thus, in this study, we want to investigate the role of social media marketing and role of graphic design in Indonesia to analyze the findings of previous researchers further. This research will be conducted through relevant methods and approaches. Aspects of communication attract attention and convey messages to the public. Therefore, this research was written so that in the future, it can be a reference for other researchers.

4. Analysis

(1) Data source and collection

Data collection in this study was assisted by using a questionnaire with a purposive sampling technique and a Five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Social Media Marketing variable was measured with 6 items from 3 indicators (content creation, community building, connecting) proposed by

(Erdogmus & Cicek, 2012). The brand Image variable was measured using 6 items from 3 indicators (corporate image, user image, product image) proposed by Keller (2009). Graphic Design variable was measured with 6 question items from 3 indicators (index, color, picture) offered by (Malvik, C, 2021). Meanwhile, to measure Brand Loyalty, 6 question items were used from 3 indicators (main choice, word of mouth, trust) proposed by Salomon (2011). A total of 250 respondents participated in this study with the respondents' criteria: were KFC consumers, had social media accounts, had seen and interacted with KFC Indonesia's official accounts in the last 6 months and had a role as decision-makers in purchasing. The demographic information was collected, namely gender, age, occupation, and monthly income.

(2) Classification of variables and identification of parameters

Data were analyzed through AMOS 26 with the Structural Equation Modeling method. Using SEM, three types of analysis activities could be carried out simultaneously. They were firstly obtaining a suitable model for predictions related to structural model analysis, secondly testing the relationship model between variables related to the measurement model, and checking the validity and reliability of instruments related to analysis. The overall fit of the model was measured by chi-square (χ^2), root mean square residual (RMR), goodness of fit index (GFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Normed Fit Index (NFI). Furthermore, SEM analysis aimed to determine whether the research hypothesis was accepted or rejected. SEM analysis displayed the t-score value for each coefficient. A hypothesis could be stated to have a causal relationship if the t-score t-table (1.96) with a significance level (generally = 0.05). Meanwhile, the indirect effect of the mediating variable was determined by carrying out the Sobel test.

Table 1 Respondent’s Characteristics

Category	Item	F	%
Age	<20	28	11.4
	21-25	213	85.2
	>25	9	3.4
	Total	250	100
Gender	Male	53	21.4
	Female	197	78.6
	Total	250	100
Occupation	University Student	87	34.8
	Employee	94	37.6
	Civil Servant	14	5.6
	Others	55	22
	Total	250	100
Income per month IDR	IDR1,000,000 - IDR1,500,000	143	57.2
	IDR 1.500.000 – IDR 2.000.000	40	16
	above IDR 2.000.000	67	26.8
	Total	250	100

Based on the description above, it can be seen that respondents were more dominated by females, average age of 21-25 years, amounting to 85.2%. Furthermore, the respondents were dominated by employees with a percentage of 94%, with a monthly income of IDR 1,000,000 – IDR 1,500,000 per month.

(3) Measurement and Stuctural Model

Table 2 Measurement Model Result

Variable	Indikator	Items	Factor Loading	CR	AVE
Social Media Marketing (Erdogmus & Cicek, 2012)	Content Creation	SMM1	0.84	0.95	0.77
		SMM2	0.90		
	Community Building	SMM3	0.88		
		SMM4	0.86		
	Connecting	SMM5	0.86		
		SMM6	0.92		
Brand Image (Keller, 2009)	Corporate Image	BI1	0.91	0.93	0.71
		BI2	0.92		
	User Image	BI3	0.84		

Graphic Design (Malvik, C ,2021)	Product Image	BI4	0.82	0.94	0.78
		BI5	0.81		
		BI6	0.75		
	Indeks	GD1	0.92		
		GD2	0.85		
	Color	GD3	0.86		
GD4		0.90			
Picture	GD5	0.88			
	GD6	0.87			
Brand Loyalty (Solomon, 2011: 646)	Main choice	BL1	0.88	0.94	0.76
		BL2	0.91		
	Word of mouth	BL3	0.89		
		BL4	0.87		
	Trust	BL5	0.85		
		BL6	0.81		

According to Table 2, the loading factor value of all items in the entire model was above 0.50. It means that the research items were considered valid and were believed to be able to measure the complete model construct.

Table 3 Index of Goodness of Fit

The goodness of Fit Index	Cut off Value	Results
χ^2	Expected to be low	704.278
Df		246
χ^2 - Significance Probability	≥ 0.05	0.000
CMIN/DF	≤ 3.00	2.863
RMR	< 0.05	0.039
IFI	≥ 0.90	0.932
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.923
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.931

The goodness of fit (GOF) measurement results in table 3 meet the requirements so that the model fit could be accepted. Table 3 shows that there were five measurements that showed a good degree of fit. CMIN/DF = 2.863 (≤ 3.00) and RMR = 0.039 (< 0.05) met the criteria. CFI = 0.931, IFI = 0.932, and TLI = 0.923; all were above 0.90 and were sufficient to state that a model was fit and appropriate.

5. Construction of Model Structure Test

Figure 1: Full Model Structure Test

Table 4 Hypothesis Testing

	Item	Std Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p-values	description
SMM	---> BI	0.226	0.061	3.728	***	Accepted
GD	---> BI	0.412	0.070	5.920	***	Accepted
SMM	---> BL	0.233	0.071	3.286	0.001	Accepted
G.D.	---> BL	0.376	0.084	4.460	***	Accepted
B.I.	---> BL	0.271	0.088	3.063	0.002	Accepted

This study was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (social media marketing, brand image, and graphic design on brand loyalty). The model examined the relationship between the 3 independent and dependent variables. The overall model was interrelated and influential in this study. Based on figure 1, table 4, the social media marketing t-score value for the brand image was 3.728, greater than the t-table value (1.96). Likewise, the p-value was less than 0.001, less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). These results were related to the first hypothesis, in which social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on brand image, where social media as a facilitator succeeds in stimulating and introducing KFC to consumers through unique and interactive content. Therefore, it can become an inherent brand image. It is in line with the opinion of previous researchers (Hilman et al., 2017; Sano, 2014; Seo & Park, 2018) and contradicts the argument of Godey et al. (2016) that SMM may not be effective enough to create a positive brand image in the consumers' mind and increase brand loyalty. However, research results varied among different groups from different countries.

In the second hypothesis, the t-score for graphic design on the brand image was 5.920, and the p-value was less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). It proves that graphic design had a positive and significant effect on the brand image of the KFC brand, in line with previous research (Leelayudthyothin, 2022). An attractive visual design would influence consumer perceptions of the company's image with a design structure, color variations, and appropriate design that would affect the company's reputation in the consumers' minds (Ageeva et al., 2018). Attractive ad designs would increase consumer perception of a brand, similar to KFC, which always uses red in every ad content design they create. It aims to maintain the image of its products by embedding the visual red color, which is the hallmark of this fast food company.

In the third hypothesis, the social media marketing t-score for brand loyalty was 3,286, and the p-value was less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). The support for this third hypothesis showed that customer perceptions of the KFC brand could be stimulated through the use of social media as a connecting platform between consumers and marketers (Ebrahim, 2019). Social media marketing is a communication tool to engage consumers and convey brand information. Therefore, KFC must be able to maintain user privacy and share reliable information, which has a major role in maintaining usage loyalty and intensity of participation in social media (Pentina et al., 2013). It is in line with what KFC is doing to maintain customer loyalty through campaigns, advertisements, interactive content, and promotions. KFC's consistency which continues to hold promos every Thursday, is also the key to KFC's success in maintaining consumer loyalty by providing information through its social media so that it can continue to build trust and eliminate uncertainty (Khadim et al., 2018; Seo & Park, 2018)

In the fourth hypothesis, the value of t - a graphic design score on brand loyalty was 4.460, and the p-value is less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). Thus, graphic design had a positive and significant effect on brand loyalty to the KFC brand. It is in line with previous research (Atak, 2021; Din et al., 2016), which states that an attractive design can provide detailed information to fulfill potential purchase intentions among online buyers. Content with visual appeal, color, innovation, and image content will stimulate an emotional response from platform users to content that will explain consumer satisfaction and lead to consumer loyalty. An attractive design aesthetic will directly influence consumer perceptions, increasing user loyalty. KFC is a fast food company that has been around for a long time and is in great demand by the public. Hence, using good and consistent graphic design in the company's content will help maintain consumer perception and loyalty that the most delicious chicken in Indonesia is KFC's chicken.

In the fifth hypothesis, the t-score value of brand image on brand loyalty was 3.063, and the p-value was less than 0.001; less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). The study results showed that brand image had a positive and significant effect on brand loyalty. When a buyer became aware of a product, he/she started repurchasing. It demonstrates that there was a direct relationship between brand image and brand loyalty. It is in accordance

with previous research (Bilgin, 2018; Arman, 202) proving that brand image increases consumer loyalty. In traditional marketing, companies use communication tools to stimulate consumer perceptions and associations with brands. Whereas modern marketing uses KFC corporate social media to increase awareness, reach new customers and enhance their brand image through communication established in published content, this will contribute to the value of KFC's Brand Image (Godey et al., 2016). Thus, various social media marketing activities are assumed to influence various consumer perceptions of loyalty (Pham & Gammoh, 2015). Therefore, when awareness about a brand increases, loyalty also increases. As a result, brand image influences brand loyalty positively. Furthermore, the indirect impact of the mediating variable is presented in Table 5, which contains the results of the Sobel test.

Tabel 5 Sobel Test – Significance of Mediation

Item				Sobel test statistic	Two-tailed probability	description	
SMM	--->	BI	--->	BL	2.368	0.017	Accepted
GD	--->	BI	--->	BL	2.728	0.006	Accepted

Based on the results of the Sobel test in Table 5, the statistical value of the social media marketing variable for brand loyalty was 2.368, and the p-value was 0.017. These results indicated that the statistical value of the Sobel test was greater than the t-table (1.96), and the p-value obtained was less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). Likewise, the statistical value of the graphic design variable on brand loyalty was 2.728 and a p-value of 0.006. The statistical value of the Sobel test results was smaller than the t-table (1.96), and the p-value obtained was less than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). It shows that there was an indirect effect of social media marketing and graphic design on brand loyalty through the brand image of the KFC brand. Consequently, it can be concluded that hypotheses six and seven can be accepted; seen from the t-score values for the two variables, they were still far below the t-score for measuring the direct effect of social media marketing and graphic design on brand loyalty. Thus, it can be stated that the indirect relationship through brand image did not significantly affect KFC consumer loyalty in Indonesia.

6. Discussion

The effects of social media marketing, brand image, and graphic design on brand loyalty show that most Indonesians are interested in the branding carried out by KFC. The habit of using social media is a powerful tool for KFC marketers to maintain the loyalty of their loyal consumers by utilizing innovative and interactive content. This research can provide information and references for fast food business people to increase consumer loyalty in Indonesia. This study has a practical implementation for managers. The results show that there is a direct relationship between brand image and customer satisfaction. Therefore, managers must improve brand image by increasing public awareness about the KFC brand. A good brand image will also increase consumer loyalty when brand awareness increases. Marketers must try various ways to create loyalty among consumers by utilizing existing social media platforms to maintain product images with quality and aesthetic content.

This research also shows that the quality of an ad is also important because it plays a role in luring consumers to glance at it. Therefore, managers must assess the advertisements that are made. It is because if the company can attract consumers, the level of consumer interest will also increase. This study also shows that brand loyalty is also an important variable. Consequently, managers must focus on social media marketing, brand image, and the quality of graphic design.

For researchers, the results of this study are expected to become literature and references to examine other dimensions that might be able to encourage loyalty by utilizing social media as a platform and source of information. Future researchers can use a broader sample and can take advantage of other industries, including luxury products. Researchers can also introduce moderators in the model.

7. Conclusions

(1) Limitation

The sample size in this study was small so that future researchers could use a larger sample. Future researchers can use broader samples and benefit from other industries, such as luxury products. Researchers can also introduce moderators in the model. This study only shows the results of one company, while future researchers may utilize multiple companies. The sample used for this study was drawn from only one city in Indonesia. Future researchers can collect data from several cities, or this model can be used in other countries.

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